

A Critical Stylistic Study of Pidgin English in Select Nigerian Stand-up Comedy Video Clips

Ivie Sarah OSAIGBOVO

Department of Languages, College of Humanities, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo

State E-mail: osaigbovosarah4@gmail.com

&

Chibuzor Franklin AKPATI (PhD)

Department of Languages, College of Humanities, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo

State E-mail: akpatichibuzor@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12808904>

ABSTRACT

This research is a study of the use of Pidgin English in selected stand up comedy video clips and how these comedians achieve their goals with words. The study also identified the Critical Stylistic features that explain the comedies of the selected comedians. The comics' choice of words is far from being incidental, superficial, or supplementary. Performers' choices of words show how their ideas are embodied in language. That is to say, the effect of how a comedian uses words and humour strategies is vital for understanding the contextual meaning of jokes and how they appeal to logic and reason. Data were obtained from videos on YouTube channels of seven comedy shows. The selected comedians are Basket mouth, Bovi, I go dye, Ali Baba, MC Shakara, Akpororo and AY. It further interpreted the analysed features and used three out of the ten critical stylistic tools which are prominent in the data. This was done with the view of investigating how Critical Stylistic tools were applied in the comedies. The data analysed were principally chosen with what we discovered to be in line with the tools. As said, the data were analysed using three of the tools which are: Naming and Describing, Hypothesizing, and Representing Time, Space and Society. Findings showed that Naming and Describing was used by the comedians to manipulate the audience, making use of Pidgin English and also passing information to them which might seem true or false but for the aim of creating humour. Hypothesizing is also used by the comedians to describe the degree of certainty about their comedy and they make use of modal auxiliaries like would, shall, should and so on to construct humorous meanings. Representing Time, Space and Society was used by the comedians to describe or explain certain time, place and social context using demonstrative pronouns and deitic words. The study so far has been able to discover the tools of critical stylistics and how they have been used to identify the words used by comedians.

Keywords: Critical stylistics; Pidgin; Video; Comedy; Nigerian

A Publication of School of Postgraduate Studies, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State

Introduction

Making the right linguistic decisions is necessary for effective communication with an audience. Knowledge of cultural backgrounds and linguistic idioms are relevant to a comedian's performance. In addition to forging a bond between the audience and the comedian, comedy affects society in a variety of ways. It teaches, corrects, challenges, affirms, undermines, and corrects shared beliefs and experiences, altering people's perspectives, emotions and behaviours regarding significant issues. We need to learn more about the social and psychological effects of comedy on modern society. Nigerian stand-up comedians must choose the right language expression to deliver amusing punchlines in this multilingual nation. Almost every Nigerian can speak or understand Nigerian Pidgin, and so, it has become the unofficial language of advertisement, entertainment, and other forms of information intended for mass consumption. Most Nigerian stand-up comedians have tactically appropriated this linguistic resource for their profession. They mostly perform in Nigerian Pidgin because they realize that performing in Standard British English would decrease the liberating effects, the size of their audience and make the jokes mechanical. They believe that Nigerian Pidgin helps in creating the amusing effects they so desire and putting across the message better. This is because in stand-up comedy, the feedback of the audience is instant and crucial for the comedian's act. An audience expects a stand-up comedian to provide a steady stream of laughs and a performer is always under pressure to deliver. Stand-up comedy is a comic style in which a comedian performs in front of a live audience, usually speaking directly to them. The performer is commonly known as a comic, stand-up comedian or simply a stand-up. The comedian recites a grouping of humorous stories, jokes and one-liners typically called a monologue. Some stand-up comedians use props, music or magic tricks to enhance their acts. Stand-up comedies are often

A Publication of School of Postgraduate Studies, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State

performed in corporate events, comedy clubs, bars and pubs, night clubs and theatres. Outside live performance, stand-up comedies are often distributed commercially via television, DVD, CD, YouTube and the Internet. Stand-up comedy in Nigeria is traced to 1993, when its founder, Allelujah Atupota Akpobome (Ali Baba) performed regularly at a Lagos nightclub. Ali Baba began professional stand-up comedy in Nigeria and incidentally, he was the favoured comedian of Nigeria's former president, Olusegun Obasanjo. He has since mentored many comedians, most notably, Ayo Makun (AY). Other successful Nigerian comedians include, but are not restricted to, Basketmouth, I Go Dye, Klint de Drunk, Lepacious Bose, and Gordons (all stage names).

1.2 English Language in Nigeria

Nigeria, a multilingual nation, is situated in West Africa. An estimated 516 indigenous languages are spoken in the country (Gordon, 2005). The role that these languages play in shaping the social and cultural beliefs and ideologies of the local populace cannot be overemphasized. However, the official language of Nigeria is British English, which is used in all spheres of life, such as for education, administration, broadcasting, formal interactions, etc. Nigerians who went to school can express themselves and understand the English language. The English language is a second language in Nigeria. Nigerians spoke their indigenous languages before the introduction of English into the country, creating contact between English as a foreign language and the local languages in Nigeria. As the saying goes, "language is culture" (Nau *et al.*, 2014), which suggests that language and culture cannot be separated from each other because cultural beliefs and social values are embedded in language. The contact between two or more languages engenders an interaction between two or more cultures. Such contacts will definitely bring about some changes in societal interaction, values, and beliefs. English came to Nigeria through many activities between Nigerians and Europeans,

such as commercial trade, the slave trade, colonisation, and missionary work, which happened in phases. Thus, it can be said that Nigerians borrowed English from the owners and converted it to more personal uses to satisfy their needs.

Many Nigerians had to learn English to work as interpreters and clerks for European companies located in Nigeria, and some returnee slaves came back knowing how to speak English. By the 18th century, English was the only European language spoken in certain areas in Nigeria, such as Calabar (Ajayi, 1965). This contact between the culture and language of Nigeria and Europeans led to the variety of English spoken in Nigeria today. Abolishing slavery (1885-1950) helped promote the spread of English in Nigeria. Many slaves returned to Nigeria with a good command of English because they had received formal education, and they entered the society with the language. Many of them were employed as teachers, messengers, clerks, and interpreters for missionaries, British colonialists, and administrators of industries (Ekpe, 2010).

There was an intense missionary activity from Europeans in Nigeria between 1843 and 1914. The aim of the missionaries was to bring the Christian gospel to a population that was predominantly pagan worshippers. The foreign missionaries needed to speak one of the local languages to communicate with the locals, and they needed to either learn one of the local languages or use an interpreter while learning the language. As this interaction continued, for the indigenous people to be able to read the Bible, they had to learn how to read and write in English. In their efforts to spread the gospel, the foreign missionaries built schools where the children of locals were taught English. In fact, the curriculum was basically the study of the English language divided into courses like reading, speaking, writing, diction, composition, and grammar (Adetugbo, 1979).

The activities of the missionaries were quite successful in the western, eastern, and southern parts of Nigeria. People from these regions welcomed Christianity, which came with missionary schools and the teaching of English language. In the south, English was readily accepted because of the multiethnic groups in the region with too many mutually unintelligible languages. Thus, English became a unifying language of communication. The contrary was the case in the north of Nigeria because of the monolithic feudal structure. They had large Emirates and shared a common language (Hausa). Missionary work in the north was not as fluid as it was in the south. During slavery, those sold to slave traders were the peasants known as talakawa, while those of royal blood or “kingmakers” called the Masu Sarata Na Asali (‘hereditary office holders’) and the Masu Sarautac na Cafka (‘holders of the office of allegiance’) were never sold. When the freed slaves from the north returned to the country, they were unable to access the elite to educate them in

However, when southern and northern Nigeria were consolidated in 1914, the north had no choice but to accept the dominance of English as the language of instruction in schools, as English was made compulsory to gain admission into schools. In 1945, the constitution made English the official language. The desire for independence saw the erection of more schools, and the demand for more teachers increased. More Nigerians were used to teach English, especially in the south, which introduced the Nigerian accent over the English accent. As English was the official language used for education, legislation, media, employment, and admission in schools, Nigerians were able to read English and European literature, and they became familiar with western culture, ideas, beliefs, and values, which led to the demand for independence in 1956 but was later achieved in 1960. Then, English language played a pivotal role in national unity and integration. The contact between English and Nigerian native languages gave birth to a local kind of English that is unique to

A Publication of School of Postgraduate Studies, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State

Nigerians. Thus, uniquely Nigerian expressions arose, such as blow horn instead of ‘honk the horn’ of a vehicle, which reflects the way the traditional horn is blown, and go slow instead of ‘traffic jam’ to reflect the slow movements of cars during traffic hold-up. This phenomenon is called ‘globalisation,’ which is the adaptation of a global outlook on local conditions (Ekpe, 2006).

Nigerian Pidgin English

The language widely spoken and understood by most Nigerians is Nigerian Pidgin English (NPE). Over 75 million people speak Nigerian Pidgin English (BBC World Service) and many more understand it. According to Farcalas (2002), Nigerian Pidgin English originated from the contact between Nigerians and European traders and missionaries, that is, English is the main contributor to NPE’s vocabulary, making NPE an English lexifier language. The substrate languages that also contributed to NPE are indigenous languages, as well as Portuguese and Dutch. When the British colonized Nigeria in the 18th century, the contact between the colonizers and the colonized created an emergency need for communication, which engendered the birth of the NPE (Elugbue & Omanor, 1991). Thus, NPE did not only originate from the contact between the indigenous people and British traders and missionaries, but also arose as the result of the communication between the colonial elite and the colonized. Furthermore, those who were not educated created a simplified form, which led to the emergence of modern NPE, a situation that from a social perspective brought about the variations in the different types of English based on the level of education, the formality of the occasion, occupation, social class, sex, and age. Thus, it is not uncommon to see Nigerians code-switching or code-mixing between English, their local languages, and the different forms of English during conversations.

The contact of English with other languages in Nigeria led to the emergence of other forms, such as NPE. These varieties are used by most of the uneducated people in the country who do not express themselves in Standard English. NPE has, over the years, gained some wide recognition as it is also used by the highly educated in informal situations. It is equally used in radio and television programmes as well as by the print media for advertisements, talk shows, drama, films, faith-based programmes, cartoons etc. A radio station based in Lagos, known as Wazobia FM, currently broadcasts all its programmes in NPE. There has been some agitation from different quarters that NPE should be made the Nigerian national language because of its extensive usage (Ekpe, 2010). In states such as Edo, Rivers, and the Delta, NPE has taken the form of a creole. Some children in these states cannot speak their native languages but can only communicate in NPE. Most speakers of NPE also indulge in code variation for easy communication or when they are in loss of words or when there is no exact equivalent in their indigenous languages or when the word is not a cultural one (Ekpe, 2010).

This present study investigated the artistic skills used by comedians to manipulate human language in order to create humour. These comedies are medicinal and have effects on the audience. They achieve this through the skillful use of Nigerian Pidgin and Nigerian English artistically to entertain the audience. Their patterns and choices of Nigerian English can sometimes have hidden meanings that depict Nigerian ways of life and their tone of utterance can sometimes be inappropriate. Different studies have been done on Nigerian comedies focusing mainly on their use of humour as comic relief, employing different discursive strategies to draw the attention of the audience. For instance, Adekunle (2014) examined satirical devices and the performativity techniques used by Nigerian Stand-up comedians. Also, Adetuyi *et al* (2018) looked at the linguistic features of Pidgin

and how comedians use them to create humour. Furthermore Filani (2015) examined Stand-up comedy as an activity type and discourse features in Stand-up comedy. The study further identified and categorized features of Pidgin in Nigerian Stand-up comedy. However, much attention has not been given to the study of comedies from the perspective of critical stylistics, hence this present study intends to fill the gap.

Linguistic Studies on Stand-up Comedies in Nigeria

The study of stand-up comedies is relatively new among Nigerian linguists, to this end, most investigators have considered it from different perspectives. Filani (2015) viewed stand-up comedy as an activity type. This means that it can be viewed as a specification of social pragmatics since it accentuates how social constraints and interactional goals influence a speaker's choice of an utterance and the hearer's favored interpretative patterns and it also creates room for how participants contributions impact the development of talk-in-interaction and it shows why and how speakers exploit a situation to achieve their interactional goals. Only the stand-up comedians are able to negotiate all the parameters of activity types. The audience are limited and cannot manipulate majority of the parameters since they perform a passive role in the stand-up comedian's interaction. It is also connected to the structure of the activity type of humor performance, which places the comedians in foregrounded position where he or she is the focus of the interaction. Adekunle (2014) examined satiric devices and the performativity techniques used by Nigerian stand-up comics, with a view to determine the role of stand-up comedy as a veritable source of socio-economic consciousness and a medium of social criticism. Thus, these versions of comic performance functions both as a cathartic device through which psychological and physical strains are eased out, and as a tool for critiquing social problems. It also proved that the conversational technique

employed by comedians in their performances served as advice giving style, counseling method and teaching aid. Filani (2019) explored how Nigerian Stand-up Comedies evoke gendered concepts in their routines. This was to examine how gender was manifested in linguistic expressions that literally have no gender undertones, that is to say, as long as words have semantic concepts and contextual variation encoded in them, the possibilities of personalising, widening, and loosening their use by the speaker are inevitable. Adetuyi *et al.*, (2018) looked at the linguistics features of pidgin and how comedians use it to create humor. This study was carried out by identifying and categorising the features of pidgin in Nigerian comedy shows, interpreting the contexts expressed by the features, and by relating the contents of humorous opinions as expressed in comedy shows. The data analysis revealed that pidgin is an informal language, and so its informality creates an equal social relationship in an informal setting which aids laughter. Comedians are able to express humour in pidgin because it is no man's native language, and as such, they could use it creatively to achieve their aim (humour). The unserious and informal nature of the language and its method of preservation make their stories humorous.

Filani and Ajayi (2019) did a linguistic analysis to identify the ideologies inherent in the jokes of Nigerian Stand-up Comedies. Based on Austin's (1962, 1975) notion that people "do things with words," it follows that comedians create humour with words, and they have to make the right choice of word to make people laugh. It is quite surprising to see that no study so far mentioned above has investigated the words used by the comedians. This study is an attempt to cover this gap in the literature by taking a linguistic analysis of the comic word choices, bring out the incongruous elements in them and the underlying sociocultural beliefs of the word choices that generate humour.

This is because words are used to achieve every linguistic expression, thereby making the choice of words an indispensable domain of investigation in every aspect of verbal communication.

Methodology

The data for this research were derived from the comedies used by the seven selected comedians Bovi, Basketmouth, I Go Dye, Ali Baba, MC Shakara, Akpororo and AY on YouTube and other Internet sources. It involved playing, and watching some of the comedies and selecting the most appropriate ones for this study. It was purposively sampled and only the comedies that were relevant to this work were selected. The sampling procedure involved playing, and watching some of the comedies and selecting the most important ones for this study. The data analysed were chosen with what we found to be correlating with the tools for critical stylistics analysis. Based on these tools, the sampling technique was used to select comedies that focus on the tools for critical stylistics. Although there are many tools, if not more than ten but the data for this study were analysed with the use of three analytical tools which are: Naming and Describing, Hypothesizing and Representing Time, Space and Society.

Theoretical Framework

Critical Stylistics

Critical stylistics is a method of analysing texts to reveal the ideological construction depending on transitivity as well as other textual practices. It is also an approach to analysing texts that focuses on the linguistic choices made by the author and their potential effects on the reader (Jeffries 2010). It involves examining the language used, such as word choice, sentence structure and rhetorical devices to uncover underlying meanings, ideologies and power dynamics within the text (Barry 2002). In abroad sense, critical stylistics seeks to understand how language shapes and reflects

social, political and cultural realities. It recognises that texts are not neutral, but rather convey specific perspectives, values and ideologies. By close examination, critical stylistics aims to uncover these hidden meanings and shed light on the ways in which language can influence our understanding and interpretation of the world (Jefferies 2010).

Tools of Critical Stylistics

Mahmood (2018) developed various tools used in critical stylistics in his dissertation on the topic in year 2018. These tools are: a. Naming and describing b. Representing actions/events/states c. Equating and contrasting d. Exemplifying and enumerating e. Prioritizing f. implying and assuming g. Negating. h. Hypothesizing i. Speech thoughts and ideas Representing time, space and society (Adapted from Mahmood, 2018)

a. Naming and Describing: The concept naming and describing is used to describe a situation or events using nominal items or groups. The use of these items gives the reader a view or picture of how the speaker sees unfolding events in a given discourse (research gate, 2022). This tool shows that there are different ways a text can describe the world. Naming and describing includes choice of nouns, modification through pre-modification and post modification. This means that noun phrases are constructed which consists of the headword and accompanied by pre or post modifying elements (Enyi 2021, p, 44).

Name Calling: This is an abusive or provocative word or expression mainly used by people to slur, and discredit others. It can be as well used to incite people to violence or cause an unhealthy atmosphere. Name calling also refers to the use of derogatory or emotionally charged labels to describe people, groups or ideas. It involves assigning negative or pejorative terms to individuals or entities in order to evoke a specific emotional response or to discredit them in the eyes of others.

A Publication of School of Postgraduate Studies, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State

Name calling is often used as a rhetorical device in persuasive speech, propaganda, or contentious discourse to undermine opponents or to bolster one's own position.

b. Hypothesizing: This tool refers to the process by which the text producer does not always provide the view of the world as it is. It shows the degree of certainty in a speaker's texts about an idea or proposition. Here, modality is used i.e modal auxiliaries such as would, shall, will, should, could, may, must, need, ought and dare. It also uses lexical verbs, for instance run, sit, sleep etc. modal verbs and adjectival structures (Enyi 2021, p. 33). Modality constructs humorous meanings in the above because the presented hypothetical proposition is deviant in some way from naturalised ideational assumptions, and therefore foregrounded (Jeffries 2010).

c. Representing Time, Space and Society: Location in time, space and society is indicated through the form of Deixis, and the four proposed types of deixis (Jeffries, 2010a). Deictic choices made in a text can construct a text world with the capacity to bring the reader into your point of view (Jeffries, 2010a, p.147), and if this constructed point of view is deviant from naturalised ideational or ideological views then there is a potential for the construction of humour. This tool shows certain time, place and social context using adverbs, pronouns (demonstrative pronouns). It also makes use of deictic words. Deictic words or expressions are known as deixis and it is a word or phrase that points to the time, place or situation in which a speaker is speaking. Words such as this, now, that, those, then, here, these e.t.c (Enyin 2021, p. 33).

Data Presentation and Analysis

Analysis in this section is anchored on three selected analytical tools: Naming and describing, hypothesizing, and representing time, space and society.

a. Naming and Describing

Example 1: Bovi's Comedy

Bill Clinton come Nigeria, he see say light no dey anywhere, Bill Clinton come tell Obasanjo 'come over to America you can even charge your phone...

Example 2: Basket Mouth's Comedy

...**Mountain of fire** catch fire, why e no go catch fire when una dey shout fire, fire, fire...

Example 3: I GO DYE's Comedy

...But I no fit forget those children wey sabi form **SWAT team for street**...

Analysis

Naming and describing here, shows how the nouns highlighted above are used to describe a state of appraisal, mockery and fake life in making the audience laugh. In example 1, the nominal group “Bill Clinton” is MH type, where “Bill” is the modifying element and “Clinton” the head word. Bovi explains, jokingly, but realistically reveals how Nigeria has been in perpetual darkness. A theme that pervades the joke lore of Nigerian stand-up comedians is that of the incessant power outages in the country, which has resulted in the country being plunged into darkness for most nights of the year. In example 2, the nominal group “Mountain of fire” is HQ. Basketmouth did not give background information on Mountain of Fire church, because he believes that most of his audience have shared knowledge about the salient features that characterise the prayer patterns of members of Mountain of Fire church. It also indicates a keen awareness, and exploitation of, shared meaning created by the same social semiotic environment. In example 3, the nominal group found in the sentence is MHQ

where “SWAT” stands as the Modifying element, “team” for Headword and “for street” as the qualifier. Here, I GO DYE just describes how little children, while playing assign roles to themselves. He specifically gave examples of children acting as SWAT team.

Name Calling

This is an abusive or provocative word or expression mainly used by people to slur, and discredit others. It can be as well used to incite people to violence or cause an unhealthy atmosphere. Name calling also refers to the use of derogatory or emotionally charged labels to describe people, groups or ideas. It involves assigning negative or pejorative terms to individuals or entities in order to evoke a specific emotional response or to discredit them in the eyes of others.

Example 1: I GO DYE’s Comedy

...Na im pastor say dat is not craze dat is **madness!**...

Example 2: AY’s Comedy

...No be dat one even pain me, we have some doctors dat are **useless**...

Example 3: Ali Baba’s Comedy

...**Oyinbo dem dey craze**, all those pipo, **idiot** dem, no wonda dem dey do like **mugu**...

Analysis

In example 1, the comedy plays on the irony of a pastor asking his members to do something “crazy” for the lord, and one of his members taking it literally by running away with the offering box. This unexpected action creates humour because it’s the opposite of what the pastor intended. When the pastor then asks the guy to come back, it adds another layer of absurdity to the situation. The humour comes from the contrast between the pastors expectation of “crazy” behaviour for the lord and the member’s literal interpretation of it. In example 2, AY explains his wife’s behaviour while in

labour, experiencing the discomfort of child birth. The humour arises from the embarrassment and awkwardness felt by the woman's husband and the gate keeper, who inadvertently witnesses the intimate scene. As the woman experiences the pains of labour, she lies on the floor with her legs wide open in an attempt to alleviate the discomfort. However, this position exposes her private parts to the gate keeper, who observes the situation, causing embarrassment for both the woman and her husband. He further emphasizes the absurdity of the situation by commenting on the ineptitude of some doctors, suggesting that they may use the pretext of medical examinations during childbirth as an opportunity to view women's bodies, including their private parts, unnecessarily. This adds another layer of humour by highlighting societal perceptions and fears surrounding medical professionals and privacy. In example 3, the comedian talks about a Nigerian man that encounters discrimination from a white person when trying to board a bus that is already full. This discrimination is likely based on racial prejudice, with the white person making assumptions or judgments based on the Nigerian man's skin colour. The humour in the sketch may come from the Nigerian comedians response to this discrimination by contrasting the behaviour of white people, particularly their perceived overindulgence of their children, with the stricter parenting style often associated with Nigerians, Ali Baba, exaggerates cultural differences for comedic effect. Additionally, the reference to Lagos being filled with lawlessness adds another layer to the humour, perhaps poking fun at the chaotic nature of city life in Nigeria compared to the perceived orderliness of the UK.

b. Hypothesizing

Example 1: Akpororo's Comedy

...**You go see dem dey fly first class** with broom, and instead of cauldron, dem dey use blender for their jazz...

Example 2: Ali Baba's Comedy

...**You go just hear 'ping' for your phone**, alert dey enter like say na rain...

Example 3: MC Shakara's Comedy

...**You go enter bus**, conductor go dey collect offering instead of fare...

Analysis

In example 1, (You **go** see dem dey fly first class) (You **will** see them flying) Akpororo talks about a scenario where Nigeria witches organizes a convention abroad. The witches are depicted in a humorous light, flying first class with brooms and using modern appliances like blenders for their magical potions. The routine playfully suggests that even witches would engage in arguments and rivalries similar to Nigerian politics, boasting about the effectiveness of their spells. The comedy ends on a positive note, highlighting the unique blend of spirituality and culture found only in Nigeria, where even a witch convention could conclude with praise and worship.

In example 2, (You **go** just hear 'ping' for your phone) (You **will** hear the sound ping on your phone) Ali Baba speculates about a scenario where everyone who owes you money suddenly decides to pay you back all at once. The routine plays on the excitement of receiving unexpected payments and the anticipation of checking one's bank balance. However, the humour takes a twist when the electricity goes out, humourously suggesting that even when NEPA (Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission) is aware of your new found wealth and decides to interrupt your celebration.

MC Shakara in example 3, (You **go** enter bus) (You **will** enter bus) emphasizes about a scene where pastors in Nigeria decide to hold their church services in 'danfo' (public transport) buses instead of

normal church buildings. The routine plays on the idea of unconventional worship settings and the unique challenges that might arise, such as collecting offerings instead of bus fares and conducting services while navigating through traffic. The humour lies in the absurdity of the situation and the juxtaposition of religious practices with everyday experiences like commuting.

c. Representing Time, Space and Society

Example 1: AY's Comedy

...I remember one time wey I dey go event for VI, dem talk say make we show for 6PM sharp...

Example 2: Basket Mouth's Comedy

...I know say **judgment day** dey sha, **Na dat time you go know say all men** are all equal...

Example 3: Bovi's Comedy

...Buhari was president 30yrs ago, he still young that year o, he come come back to be president again...

Analysis

Example 1, AY recounts a personal experience of arriving early to an event in Victoria Island (VI) after being told to be punctual at 6PM. However, upon arrival at 5:30PM, he finds only security personnel and lizards waiting, highlighting the discrepancy between expected and actual arrival times. He then discusses "Naija time", where people often arrive significantly later than the agreed upon time due to various excuses like traffic.

In Example 2, Basketmouth captures complaints, accusations, condemnations, statements, agreements, sympathy and regrets. The comedian describes the condition under which the judgment day will look like. He states that he knows that day will be tough. He emphasizes that all men will realise that they are equal before God's eyes. He states and describes the reactions of others awaiting

A Publication of School of Postgraduate Studies, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State

judgment, as they heard his name was found in the book of life. The comedian overlooks the people's opinion and protest concerning him making heaven on the last day, so long as his name is found in the Book of Life. He opposes and refuses to listen to the audience or others awaiting judgment. The comedian goes ahead to state how Jesus would take good care of him when he finally enters heaven. He describes the scenario joyfully. The comedian demonstrates how the audience will be informing Jesus that he is bad, and protesting why he should make heaven. He also knows that that day would be tough. However, the situation of toughness is not explicitly stated to the listeners. He only describes the situation by stating that he knows how it will look like. Nonetheless, the comedian indirectly reminds or preaches to the audience about the difficulties of the judgment day. The comedian reminds all that all men will stand one day to give account of how they spent their lives on earth. He states the fact that all men will be regarded as equal by God.

In example 3, Bovi expresses himself when he told Okey Bakassi to leave comedy for young boys like himself, but Bakassi responded by reminding him that if Buhari could not leave the president seat for young Nigerian why would he retire. There is an intended transfer of emotions from the comedian to the audience. In the comedy, Bovi narrates the pain they experience as comedians: they can be loud on stage, but humble at home and show great emotional appeal to their partners. The time found in the comedy is "30 years ago" and the place "Okey Bakassi's home".

Findings

This research shows clearly how the tools of Critical Stylistics can be used to explain the use of Nigerian Pidgin by Comedians while performing. Name Calling is also used on the subject of comedian's jokes to create humour or deflate character for corrective purposes. This may elicit positive or negative reactions from the audience, depending on who is involved. The language of

comedy makes use of exaggerations to drive home its points, as some of the ideas being expressed are obviously unrealistic or exaggerated. This literary device helps to create laughter as well as present ideas for the sake of imaginative thinking. Sarcastic language characterizes the language of comedy. The use of such literary device mocks the subject of discourse and lampoons certain ills or behaviours that are considered negative to the society. The language of comedy is often spoken with hidden meanings which often are created for exposing the Nigerian ways of life, attitude and living. Rude, offensive, inconsiderate, foul, and the use of sexual or earthly languages characterize the comedian's choice of vocabularies. Code-switching, which uses a blend of Nigerian Pidgin and Standard English, and the use of physical demonstrations also create humorous effect on the audience. The effect of the language of comedy is often laughter. However, it can be observed that not all the members of the audience find a piece of joke amusing. Using the selected tools of Critical Stylistics, the style, effects and hidden meanings of Nigerian Stand-up Comedians were discovered and highlighted. Although, there are 10 tools of critical stylistics, only three were selected for the analysis and these three were used for the analysis of the comedies of the selected comedians.

Conclusion

This research, investigating the use of NP in comedies discovers how comedians use language to create laughter. Nigerian stand-up comedians have been able to achieve unique success with the use of NP. Even though it would be assumed that most of (if not all) the members of the audiences are literate and so should understand English, the comedians have felt it necessary to perform in NP, since this informal language is the most widely used and understood variety in Nigeria's multilingual society. Yet, the pre-eminence of NP clearly excludes members of the audience who are

not very versatile in this language (especially non-Nigerians) from independently processing the meanings intended by the performances. The study so far has been able to discover the tools for critical stylistics and how they have been used to identify and analyse the study of Pidgin English in Stand-up comedies in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Abe, N.A. (2014). A Linguistic Stylistic Analysis of the Language of Humour in Opa Williams “*Nite of a Thousand Laughs*”. An M.A Thesis, Department of Languages. Ahmadu Bello University. 28-32.
- Adedoyin, A. (2022). From *Alarinjo* to *Oniduro*: Stand-up Comedy as a Neo-Cultural Expression in Nigeria. 1(10), 26-27.
- Adekunle, I.J. (2014). Satiric Performativity of Stand-up Comedy in Nigeria. An M.Phil Thesis, Department of Languages, University of Ibadan 18-20
- Adetuyi, C.A., Jegede, O.O & Adeniran, A.A., (2018). Linguistic Features of Pidgin in Stand-up Comedy in Nigeria. *World Journal of English Language*. 8(2) 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wjel.v8n2pl>
- Elugbe, B.O. & Omamor A.P. (1991). *Nigerian Pidgin: (background and prospects)*. Heinemann Educational Books. ISBN: 9781291737, 97897781291739. 20-21.
- Emachi, O. (2005). *Communicative Qualities on Nigerian Pidgin*, Enugu: State University Press.
- Enyi, P.U. (2021). Critical Stylistics Analysis of Twitter Users’ Comments on the End SARS Protest in Nigeria. A B.A project, Department of Languages, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria.
- Filani, I. (2015). Discourse Types in Stand-up Comedy Performances: An example of Nigerian Stand-up Comedy. *The European Journal of Humour Research*, 3(1) 46-47.
- Filani, I. (2015). Stand-up Comedy as an Activity Type. *Israeli Journal of Humour Research*. 4(1) 79-83.
- Filani, I. (2016). Humour Strategies in Nigerian Stand-Up Comedy. PhD Thesis, University of Ibadan, Ibadan

- Ibrahim, M. (2018). *The Construction of the Speaker and Fictional World in the Small Mirrors: A Critical Stylistics Analysis*. A Doctoral Thesis, Department of Languages, University of Huddersfield
- Jimoh, J.B. (2022). *Linguistic Expressions of Pidgin English in Nigerian Stand-up Comedies*. A Doctoral Theses, Department of Modern Languages, University of Mississippi. 13-20.
- Macaulay, M. & Emmanuel O.E. (2020). Linguistic Devices and Rhetorical Strategies in Nigerian Stand-up Comedy. *Abraka Humanities Review*, 2(1), 109-115.

